

The Degree of Customers' Satisfaction with Asiacell Services in Iraq

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Abstract

The purpose of this research is to find out the degree of customers' satisfaction with the services offered by Asiacell in Iraq. The instrument for collecting data was distributing a questionnaire on WhatsApp. It was distributed randomly to users of Telecommunication Company called Asiacell. Statistical analysis was done by using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) were Regression, T-test, Anova, and Correlation were addressed. The conclusion reached was that customers are satisfied with the services offered by Asiacell such as (Internet, Dealing with users, Clarity of calls, and Prices).

Key Words: Satisfaction, Asiacell, Telecommunication, Curriculum, Knowledge, Skills, Distinguished Teachers.

Introduction

Asiacell is the first telecommunication company in Iraq that provides quality mobile and data services. Asiacell offers its services in all Iraq's governorates and 99% of the population are using Asiacell services. Asiacell were the winner of "Outstanding Contribution to the Mobile Industry Award" in 2017 (Asiacell - 2017).

The services by Asiacell include internet, Dealings with users, calls clarity, and prices.

Study Objectives

The Objectives of this study are:

- 1- To figure out the degree of the customers' satisfaction with the services offered by Asiacell Iraq.
- 2- To find out the degree of customers' satisfaction with the internet offered by Asiacell Iraq.
- 3- To determine the degree of customers' satisfaction with the quality of Dealings with the users by Asiacell Iraq.
- 4- To discover the degree of customers' satisfaction with the call's clarity of Asiacell Iraq.
- 5- To reveal the degree of customers' satisfaction with the prices offered by Asiacell Iraq.
- 6- To show the CEO of Asiacell the results and the recommendations of the research for improvement.

Significance:

This research is important because it will show the degree of customers' satisfaction with the services offered by Asiacell Iraq. In addition, it will show the least popular factor of customers' satisfaction to help improve the telecommunication in Iraq by informing the CEO the results founded.

Study Model:

Ho: Customers are not satisfied with the services offered by Asiacell in Iraq at a significant level of ($\alpha=0.05$).

Ho1: Customers are not satisfied with the internet offered by Asiacell in Iraq at a significant level of ($\alpha=0.05$).

Ho2: Customers are not satisfied with the quality of dealings with users of Asiacell in Iraq at a significant level of ($\alpha=0.05$).

Ho3: Customers are not satisfied with the calls' clarity of Asiacell in Iraq at a significant level of ($\alpha=0.05$).

Ho4: Customers are not satisfied with the prices offered by Asiacell in Iraq at a significant level of ($\alpha=0.05$).

Literature Review

In 1993, Anderson and Sullivan stated that customer's satisfaction depends on the services provided by any company. As we all know that if the company provides bad services such as low-quality internet, customers won't be satisfied with the company services. In 1999, Eklof, Hack, and Westund have done a study and mentioned the same things and said that customer's satisfaction can be measured by the services.

In 1994, the study of Anderson, Fornell, and Lehmann showed that customer's satisfaction led to high profitability and to the success of the company. It also showed that there is a relationship between customer's satisfaction and company assets. Therefore, when the customers are satisfied, the company reputation will go up and more customers will come to the company. Therefore, the profitability will be more and the company will be more successful.

"Customer satisfaction should be considered a vital component of any business because it provides marketers and business owners with a metric that can be used to measure and improve business performance from a customer perspective" (Ben, 2017). The more the customers are satisfied, the better the company performance will be.

In 2021, Rao, Saleem, Saeed, and Haqj mentioned that during Covid-19, almost all the services become online which is a new thing for both customers and individuals. So, testing the online service is important to see whether the customers are satisfied with it or not. This can be a new way of satisfaction. Companies have to make sure that customers are satisfied with the company offers.

In 1990, Reichheld and Sasser have mentioned that good services lead to better customer retention. When a company provides good services, customers will keep using the company's services. In 2009, Wicks and Rcethlein mentioned the same thing in their study and said that good quality service led to high customer loyalty.

In 2013, Hemmat defines the service as an "activity or benefit offers one party to other party". Indeed Edited Team stated that offering good services is very important as it increases the sales, increases the company's reputation, it strengthens the brand, and it attracts high-quality employees.

In 2014, IRF mentioned that the number of Iraqis using internet is increasing reaching 2.211.860 by 2012. So, offering high-quality internet services is very important as most of the people are using it in their work and daily life activities.

In 2018, Abdullah mentioned that prices have a high impact on the customer's satisfaction. One of the most important services that all the company is offering is the price. The more suitable the prices are, the more satisfied the customers will be, and the better the company's sales will be.

Asiacell

Asiacell is the first telecommunication company in Iraq. It was founded in 1999 by Faruk Mustafa Rasool. In 2020, Asiacell ranked as the best telecommunication company and it provides services for all Iraqi governorate

including Baghdad and 99% of the population are using its services. Asiacell is providing the best internet with 3.9G services. In addition, it provides 24/ 7 service to support customers’ needs (Asiacell, 2020).

Asiacell won many awards. In 2014, Asiacell won “The Beat Corporate Social Responsibility”. They also won “Dubai- based Telecom” in 2016. In addition, Asiacell won “Corporate Social Responsibility Campaign” in 2016. They won “Outstanding Contribution to the Mobile Industry Award” in 2017. Asiacell is always stand at the top when it comes to award as it is one of the best telecommunication services. Therefore, The Iraqi Ministry of Communications recognized Asiacell as the “best GSM operator” in Iraq (Asiacell 2017).

Research Methodology

Nature of research:

This research is classified as descriptive, analytical and quantitative because it measures the degree of customers’ satisfaction with Asiacell services. In this research numerical data was collected and analyzed threw distributing a questionnaire.

Population of study:

The population of the study are the users of Asiacell in Iraq, and 99% of the people of Iraq are using its services. A random sample of (230) users are picked up and only (65) users responded to the questionnaire.

Reliability

Cronbach Alpha measures internal consistency between variables and the results should be more than 0.70. In this study Cronbach Alpha is greater than (0.88) therefore the questionnaire is valid. The fifth Likert Scale (Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree, Strongly Agree) was used.

Table 1: Cronbach Alpha

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.888	.929	4

65 responds were gathered, and all of them were valid. The majority were female (60%), and the age categories were (20-29) and (40-49) were equal respondents, and 50 and above were the least. The respondents’ nationality was (92.3%) Iraqi, and almost half of the sample holds bachelor degrees (49.2%), and (78.5%) of them are employed.

Demographic Variables Analysis

Table 2: Demographic variables of the sample

		Male/Female	Iraqi/Non-Iraqi	Age	Qualifications	Employed/UnEmployed
N	Valid	65	65	65	65	65
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		1.6000	1.0769	2.2462	4.1538	1.2154
Std. Error of Mean		.06124	.03331	.12791	.10103	.05139
Median		2.0000	1.0000	2.0000	4.0000	1.0000
Mode		2.00	1.00	1.00 ^a	4.00	1.00
Std. Deviation		.49371	.26854	1.03124	.81453	.41429
Variance		.244	.072	1.063	.663	.172
Skewness		-.418	3.251	.188	-1.188	1.418
Std. Error of Skewness		.297	.297	.297	.297	.297
Kurtosis		-1.884	8.840	-1.167	2.564	.009

Std. Error of Kurtosis	.586	.586	.586	.586	.586
Range	1.00	1.00	3.00	4.00	1.00
Minimum	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Maximum	2.00	2.00	4.00	5.00	2.00
Sum	104.00	70.00	146.00	270.00	79.00

Table 3: Frequency Table for Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	26	40.0	40.0	40.0
	Female	39	60.0	60.0	100.0
	Total	65	100.0	100.0	

Figure 1: Pie Chart for Gender

Table 4: Frequency Table for Nationality

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Iraqi	60	92.3	92.3	92.3
	Non-Iraqi	5	7.7	7.7	100.0
	Total	65	100.0	100.0	

Figure 2: Pie Chart for Nationality

Table 5: Frequency Table for Age

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	20-29	20	30.8	30.8	30.8
	30-39	17	26.2	26.2	56.9
	40-49	20	30.8	30.8	87.7
	50<	8	12.3	12.3	100.0
	Total	65	100.0	100.0	

Figure 3: Pie Chart for Age

Table 6: Frequency Table for Qualifications

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Secondary	1	1.5	1.5	1.5
	Diploma	1	1.5	1.5	3.1
	Higher_Diploma	8	12.3	12.3	15.4
	Bachelor	32	49.2	49.2	64.6
	Graduate_Studies	23	35.4	35.4	100.0
	Total	65	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4: Pie Chart for Qualifications

Table 7: Frequency Table for employment

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Employed	51	78.5	78.5	78.5
	Un-Employed	14	21.5	21.5	100.0
	Total	65	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5: Pie Chart for Employment

Data Analysis

Regression

Table 8: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	1.000 ^a	1.000	1.000	0.00000

R 2 and R square adjusted explain the strength of the relationship of the variables of the dependent and independent. Since, R=1.000 and R 2 =1.000 suggesting that the independent variables can explain 100% of the variability in the dependent variable.

T- test

**Table 9: T-test for all variables
One- Sample Statistic**

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
INTERNET	65	25.2615	5.66590	.70277
CALL_QUAL	65	13.9846	3.71438	.46071
CALL	65	33.0769	7.59380	.94190
PRICE	65	28.1077	7.69156	.95402

The use of the T-test is for inferential statistic and it is used to determine if there is a significant difference between the means of two groups. With the obtained results, it states that there is a significant relationship among the dependent and independent variables.

**Table 10: T-test for all variables
One- Sample test**

	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
INTERNET	35.946	64	.000	25.26154	23.8576	26.6655
CALL_QUAL	30.354	64	.000	13.98462	13.0642	14.9050
CALL	35.117	64	.000	33.07692	31.1953	34.9586
PRICE	29.462	64	.000	28.10769	26.2018	30.0136

There is significance (2-tailed) since the (p-value for all variables =0.000≤0.05).

ANOVA

Table 11: ANOVA Test

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
PRICE	Between Groups	3698.829	40	92.471	25.388	.000
	Within Groups	87.417	24	3.642		
	Total	3786.246	64			
INTERNET	Between Groups	2006.387	40	50.160	24.993	.000
	Within Groups	48.167	24	2.007		
	Total	2054.554	64			
CALL_QUAL	Between Groups	860.068	40	21.502	22.518	.000
	Within Groups	22.917	24	.955		
	Total	882.985	64			
CALL	Between Groups	3531.615	40	88.290	13.327	.000

Within Groups	159.000	24	6.625		
Total	3690.615	64			

ANOVA helps with figuring out if we should accept or reject the null hypothesis. The results here show that there is a significant relationship among the variables since it is $(0.000 \leq 0.05)$.

Testing the Hypothesis:

Ho: Customers are not satisfied with the services offered by Asiacell in Iraq at the level of $(\alpha=0.05)$.

A significance was founded since p-value in the above tests is $=0.000 \leq 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Ho1: Customers are not satisfied with the internet offered by Asiacell in Iraq at the level of $(\alpha=0.05)$.

The null hypothesis was rejected and the correlation coefficient states that there is a significant relation at confidence interval at 0.01.

**Table 12: Correlations
Internet**

		Asiacell offers high-quality internet.	The download speed of Asiacell internet service is good.	The monthly unlimited 4G internet packages are perfect.	Asiacell provides strong WIFI signals.	Happy with the coverage of Asiacell mobile internet.	Asiacell Internet Recharge Card is useful.	Asiacell offers many internet packages.
Asiacell offers high-quality internet.	Pearson Correlation	1	.702**	.438**	.523**	.563**	.463**	.210
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.093
	N	65	65	65	65	65	65	65
The download speed of Asiacell internet service is good.	Pearson Correlation	.702**	1	.593**	.613**	.675**	.599**	.440**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	65	65	65	65	65	65	65
The monthly unlimited 4G internet packages are perfect.	Pearson Correlation	.438**	.593**	1	.653**	.731**	.687**	.625**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	65	65	65	65	65	65	65
Asiacell provides strong WIFI signals.	Pearson Correlation	.523**	.613**	.653**	1	.656**	.659**	.554**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	65	65	65	65	65	65	65
Happy with the coverage of Asiacell mobile internet.	Pearson Correlation	.563**	.675**	.731**	.656**	1	.708**	.661**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	65	65	65	65	65	65	65
Asiacell Internet Recharge Card is	Pearson Correlation	.463**	.599**	.687**	.659**	.708**	1	.541**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

useful.	N	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65
Asiacell offers many internet packages.	Pearson Correlation	.210	.440**	.625**	.554**	.661**	.541**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.093	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000		
	N	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 6: Satisfaction with the Internet Services

Note: This scatterplot indicates an upward line, indicating that there is a positive relationship. Meaning that there is high satisfaction from Asiacell consumers towards the internet services.

Ho2: Customers are not satisfied with the quality of customer service of Asiacell Iraq at the level of (a=0.05).

The null hypothesis was rejected and the correlation coefficient states that there is a significant relation at confidence interval at 0.01.

**Table 13: Correlations
Quality of Dealings with users**

		Asiacell staff understand my needs.	They responded quickly to my needs.	Asiacell staff provide complete information.	Asiacell staff provide accurate information.	Happy with the speed my call was answered.	Asiacell provide 24/7 services.	Asiacell staff have good communication skills.	My problems are solved in one call.	I have more than one tool to communicate with the customers service (call/internet).
Asiacell staff understand my needs.	Pearson Correlation	1	.847**	.793**	.749**	.789**	.621**	.634**	.675**	.430**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	N	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65
They respond quickly to my needs.	Pearson Correlation	.847**	1	.724**	.689**	.815**	.571**	.508**	.500**	.369**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0		0	0	0	0	0	0	0.003
	N	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65

Asiacell staff provide complete information.	Pearson Correlation	.793**	.724**	1	.935**	.695**	.807**	.712**	.707**	.550**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	0		0	0	0	0	0	0
	N	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65
Asiacell staff provide accurate information.	Pearson Correlation	.749**	.689**	.935**	1	.673**	.817**	.658**	.652**	.512**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	0	0		0	0	0	0	0
	N	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65
Happy with the speed my call was answered.	Pearson Correlation	.789**	.815**	.695**	.673**	1	.616**	.651**	.644**	.618**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	0	0	0		0	0	0	0
	N	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65
Asiacell provides 24/7 services.	Pearson Correlation	.621**	.571**	.807**	.817**	.616**	1	.715**	.658**	.562**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	0	0	0	0		0	0	0
	N	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65
Asiacell staff have good communication skills.	Pearson Correlation	.634**	.508**	.712**	.658**	.651**	.715**	1	.674**	.500**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	0	0	0	0	0		0	0
	N	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65
My problems are solved in one call.	Pearson Correlation	.675**	.500**	.707**	.652**	.644**	.658**	.674**	1	.573**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		0
	N	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65
I have more than one tool to communicate with the customers service (call/internet).	Pearson Correlation	.430**	.369**	.550**	.512**	.618**	.562**	.500**	.573**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	0.003	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	N	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 7: Satisfaction with the Quality of Dealings with users

Note: This scatterplot indicates an upward line, indicating that there is a positive relationship. Meaning that there is high satisfaction from Asiacell users towards the customer service.

Ho3: Customers are not satisfied with the call’s clarity of Asiacell Iraq at the level of ($\alpha=0.05$).

The null hypothesis was rejected and the correlation coefficient states that there is a significant relation at confidence interval at 0.01.

**Table 13: Correlations
Quality of Calls’ clarity**

		My experience is always positive with the call’s clarity.	Satisfied with rooming call’s clarity.	Asiacell offers high- quality calls in places that have no signals.	Asiacell provides high- quality calls coverage.
My experience is always positive with the call’s clarity.	Pearson Correlation	1	.573**	.753**	.679**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0	0	0
	N	65	65	65	65
Satisfied with rooming call’s clarity.	Pearson Correlation	.573**	1	.782**	.709**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	0	0	0
	N	65	65	65	65
Asiacell offers high- quality calls in places that have no signals.	Pearson Correlation	.753**	.782**	1	.810**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	0		0
	N	65	65	65	65
Asiacell provides high- quality calls coverage.	Pearson Correlation	.679**	.709**	.810**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	0	0	
	N	65	65	65	65

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 8: Satisfaction with the calls' Clarity

Note: This scatterplot indicates an upward line, indicating that there is a positive relationship. Meaning that there is high satisfaction from Asiacell consumers towards the customer service.

Ho4: Customers are not satisfied with the prices offered by Asiacell in Iraq at the level of (a=0.05).

The null hypothesis was rejected and the correlation coefficient states that there is a significant relation at confidence interval at 0.01.

Table 14: Correlations Prices

		Asiacell internet prices are affordable.	Satisfied with Asiacell offers.	Happy with the services offered compared to the prices paid.	Easy online payment process.	Availability of more than one payment method.	Calls prices are affordable.	Texts prices are affordable.	Prices does not include sales tax.
Asiacell internet prices are affordable.	Pearson Correlation	1	.792**	.777**	.790**	.672**	.711**	.722**	.632**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	N	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65
Satisfied with Asiacell offers.	Pearson Correlation	.792**	1	.887**	.679**	.575**	.659**	.653**	.632**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0		0	0	0	0	0	0
	N	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65
Happy with the services offered compared to the prices paid.	Pearson Correlation	.777**	.887**	1	.731**	.704**	.685**	.665**	.696**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	0		0	0	0	0	0
	N	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65
Easy online payment process.	Pearson Correlation	.790**	.679**	.731**	1	.772**	.736**	.808**	.691**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	0	0		0	0	0	0
	N	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65
Availability of more than one payment method.	Pearson Correlation	.672**	.575**	.704**	.772**	1	.692**	.648**	.704**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	0	0	0		0	0	0

	N	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65
Calls prices are affordable.	Pearson Correlation	.711**	.659**	.685**	.736**	.692**	1	.816**	.660**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	0	0	0	0		0	0
	N	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65
Texts prices are affordable.	Pearson Correlation	.722**	.653**	.665**	.808**	.648**	.816**	1	.589**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	0	0	0	0	0		0
	N	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65
Prices does not include sales tax.	Pearson Correlation	.632**	.632**	.696**	.691**	.704**	.660**	.589**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	N	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 9: Satisfaction with the Prices

Note: This scatterplot indicates an upward line, indicating that there is a positive relationship. Meaning that there is high satisfaction from Asiacell consumers towards the prices.

Delimitations:

Time was one of the main delimitations faced. Running after Asiacell users was one and convincing them to fill up the questionnaire is another thing. It took many days to distribute and collect the questionnaire. Moreover, lack of previous studies regarding the satisfaction of the users of Asiacell is another delimitation.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, according to the statistical analysis, all the null hypotheses were rejected meaning that customers are satisfied with the services (internet, quality of dealings with users, calls clarity, and prices) offered by Asiacell Iraq. This research paper can approve that Asiacell is one of the best telecommunication services in Iraq.

Recommendations and Future Research

The study recommends Asiacell’s CEO to enhance the internet speed, roaming calls’ clarity, and call’s prices since the percentages of people who are not satisfied with them are around 20%. In addition, this research paper can help CEO to increase the percentages of customers’ satisfaction by enhancing the services. For example, raising the 70% satisfied to 90%.

A future research can be done by investigating the degree of satisfaction of the Asiacell employees in Iraq towards Asiacell.” Moreover, I would recommend future research to cover more services such as “ASIA Hawala.”

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- <http://www.irfad.org/iraq-internet-use/>
- <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.751854/full>
- <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/10107082/>
- <https://digitalcommons.bryant.edu/manjou/6/>
- <https://www.theseus.fi/handle/10024/146823>

The Degree of Customers' Satisfaction with Asiacell Services in Iraq Questionnaire

Dear Consumers,

I am doing this research paper to measure the degree of customer's satisfaction toward Asiacell services in Iraq. Please fill up the questionnaire. Noting that all of your answers will be kept secret, and it will be used for research purpose only.

Thank you for your cooperation.

Supervisor:

Prof. Mohammed Abu Yaman Al Omari

Researcher:

Khadeeja Alobossi

***First: Personal information:**

1-Gender:

- Male
- Female

2-Nationality:

- Iraqi
- Non- Iraqi

3-Age:

- 20- 29
- 30- 39
- 40- 49
- 50 & above

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4-Qualifications:

- Secondary
- Diploma
- Bachelor
- Higher Diploma
- Graduate studies

5-Employment:

- Employed
- Not employed

***Second: The following statements of the questionnaire measure the degree of the customers' satisfactions toward Asiacell services in Iraq. Please tick () on the appropriate place:**

No.	Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Strongly Agree	Agree
Internet:						
1	Asiacell offers high-quality internet.					
2	The download speed of Asiacell internet service is good.					
3	The monthly-unlimited 4G internet packages are perfect.					
4	Asiacell provides strong WIFI signals.					
5	Happy with the coverage of Asiacell mobile internet.					
6	Asiacell Internet Recharge Card is useful.					
7	Asiacell offers many internet packages.					
Quality of Dealings/ Call Center:						
8	Asiacell staff understand my needs.					
9	They respond quickly to my needs.					
10	Asiacell staff provide complete information.					
11	Asiacell staff provide accurate information.					
12	Happy with the speed my call was answered.					
13	Asiacell provides 24/7 services.					
14	Asiacell staff have good communication skills.					
15	My problems are solved in one call.					
16	I have more than one tool to communicate with the customers' service (call/ internet).					
Calls Clarity:						
17	My experience is always positive with the call's clarity.					
18	Satisfied with rooming call's clarity.					
19	Asiacell offers high- quality calls in places that have no signals.					
20	Asiacell provides high- quality calls coverage.					
Prices:						
21	Asiacell internet prices are affordable.					
22	Satisfied with Asiacell offers.					
23	Happy with the services offered compared to the prices paid.					
24	Easy online payment process.					
25	Availability of more than one payment method.					
26	Calls prices are affordable.					
27	Texts prices are affordable.					
28	Prices does not include sales tax.					